

SPORT AND HEALTHY LIFESTYLE

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Abstract: *This article examines the attitude of people to the formation of a healthy image life. In the article, the phenomenon of a healthy lifestyle is presented as a specific form expedient human activity - activities aimed at preserving, strengthening and improving his health. Attention is focused on the side of physical activity and the desire to her choice of food and a responsible attitude to the formation of dietary habits. In the work also shows the possibilities for people in the field of physical activity. The positive influence from the outside on the attitude to a healthy lifestyle is considered.*

Keywords— healthy lifestyle, health, beauty.

1. INTRODUCTION

A healthy lifestyle is not possible without movement. Let's make a reservation right away that by sports we mean not heavy physical training to achieve sports results. Rather, it is physical exercise to keep your body fit, feel great and prevent aging. If you choose only proper nutrition from the whole range of healthy lifestyle measures, this will give a result, but it will not be so obvious. Daily exercise is essential for health and beauty. You can load yourself more twice a week, and for the rest of the days, choose a set of not heavy exercises. First, decide on your main sport. Choose only your favorite! If you exercise on the treadmill without experiencing any pleasure until you lose consciousness, it will not bring results. Be sure to eat before your workout so as not to pounce on food immediately after exercise. But the food should be very light: something vegetable or fruit. The benefits of playing sports are obvious: muscles are tightened, the skin is better supplied with blood, which gives youth, you can burn extra calories and, accordingly, lose weight. So, we choose sports activities to our liking.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

Useful if you run evenly all the time, it is advisable to run at least 4 km. It has a good effect on the figure, tightens the hips, buttocks, improves blood supply, while running, you can get distracted from pressing problems, this relieves nervous tension. If you are unhappy with your figure, you can choose places with fewer people. Undoubted advantage: availability, relatively high consumption of calories, if you run 4 km in half an hour, up to 500 kilocalories are spent. But with this choice, additional gymnastics classes are desirable. Jumping rope: the simplest and most effective way to keep in shape. Jumping can even replace gymnastics! Despite the apparent uniformity of movements, almost all 114 muscles work, posture improves. The buttocks are tightened, the hips are strengthened, the muscles of the arms are tense. Blood circulation improves, heart rate accelerates. Suitable for absolutely everyone, but do not start with heavy loads, this can adversely affect the heart, you must be careful when dealing with vascular diseases of the

legs. It burns up to 1000 calories per hour, but here it depends strongly on the loads. The undoubted advantage is accessibility. But not everyone will go outside to jump, and jumping on the ninth floor of an overweight high-rise building is problematic. Nordic walking: walking with special poles, an open-air sport available to everyone. This technique allows you to activate about 90% of all muscles in our body, as well as the arms, upper body and legs, achieving a more effective result than with normal walking. Especially Scandinavian walking is beneficial for older people. Nordic walking keeps people in good shape and, without exaggeration, brings people with musculoskeletal problems back to life. This is the best activity for losing weight naturally (without tiring diets). Exercises are shown all year round, in particular - in winter and summer. The result is achieved naturally - through rhythmic movement and proper breathing of clean air in nature. High blood pressure and high cholesterol levels contribute to the development of heart disease, and regular walking helps to fight it.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Walking puts less stress on your joints than more active activities like running or aerobics. However, it helps to reduce the risk of osteoporosis, and the chances of falling while walking are much less likely. Tourism: suitable for office workers who spend all day at the computer. If you can't imagine a day without communication, tourism is for you! Rugged terrain, low mountains, and hiking are ideal for toning your thighs and abdominal muscles. Beautiful countryside, great air. Good pictures can be taken. Amateur tourists cover an average of 30 km per day. And then songs with a guitar. Perhaps sleeping in the fresh air. You can take your grown-up children with you. Burns up to 400 kilocalories per hour. Disadvantage: the impossibility of hiking in winter, it is difficult to find time (this is not two hours a week!). Bicycle: calves are pumped up, buttocks are strengthened and acquire a beautiful shape, blood supply improves. Many families have bicycles. Bicycles are bought for children. You can even ride a bike to work! It is burned up to 600 kcal per hour. But there are also disadvantages - Belarusian cities are not suitable for cyclists. We do not have dedicated lanes, our car owners do not

take into account the cyclists, we have no parking spaces for bicycles.

4. CONCLUSION

The summer is too short, you will not ride a bike in slush and snow. Of course, there are fitness equipment, but not everyone has the opportunity to visit the gyms. And to buy a home is expensive and takes up a lot of space. And the effect is not at all the same. For sports, you need special sportswear. Almost any clothing can be either elite class or budget options. If you are serious, then you need to get it.

5. REFERENCES

- [1] Eisenberg K. Football as a global phenomenon. Historical perspectives / per. with him. L. Kortunova // LOGOS. 2006. No. 3. P. 93–103.
- [2] Blatter J. The FIFA Family (from the report at the 54th Ordinary FIFA Congress in Paris in May 2004) // Football Industry. 2004. No. 3. p. 6-13.
- [3] Hornby N. Football fever: a novel / trans. from English A. Sokolova. M. : Inostranka, 2003.335 p.
- [4] Almekaimi H. The effect of soccer organizational structure in Kuwait and other Gulf countries on the relationship between attendance and soccer team performance. University of Minnesota, 2005.197 p.